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Abstract

This study investigates the impact of supervisor's phubbing (the act of ignoring subordinates by focusing more on mobile devices) on project success within the construction industry, considering NESPAK projects. Construction projects are exceptionally complicated and high-risk, often confronting challenges in fulfilling their allocated cost, schedule, and quality goals. One of the noticeable barriers to success is poor communication, with supervisor's phubbing appearing as a recent manifestation of this problem. This research explores how phubbing affects project outcomes, concentrating on the roles of psychological distress, emotional engagement, and employee resilience. Referring to the existing literature and based on empirical data, the study examines how supervisor's phubbing contributes to psychological strain and

disengagement among team members, ultimately hindering project performance. It also explores how employee resilience can help buffer these negative effects. Data was collected from NESPAK employees using structured questionnaires, and analyzed through linear regression, correlation analysis, and structural equation modeling using SPSS. The findings have demonstrated that supervisor's phubbing negatively impacts project success, with psychological distress and emotional engagement acting as partial mediators, and employee resilience serving as a moderator. This study adds valuable empirical evidence to existing literature and offers practical insights for improving communication and leadership practices in construction project management.

Keywords: Supervisor Phubbing, Project Success, Emotional Engagement, Psychological Distress, Employee Resilience

Introduction

The extensive use of smartphones has considerably enriched communication and productivity in contemporary life, nevertheless it has also brought novel challenges within organizational and managerial contexts. One of the most appearing concerns is the inclination of supervisors to check or use their phones during communications with subordinates, a behavior referred to as supervisor phubbing (Lievaart, 2020). This practice interrupts face-to-face communication and weakens the quality of supervisor-subordinate relationships, generally leading to disengagement and lower

performance (Koç & Çalışkan Akbıyık, 2022). The present study focuses on the impact of supervisor's phubbing on construction project success, an environment where communication plays a significant part in coordinating complicated and high-risk tasks.

Defining project success always remained a debatable point for scholars and practitioners. However, a commonly established framework identifies success through the completion of a project within its allocated time, cost, and quality, together all these factors known as the "iron triangle" (Zid et al., 2020). Overall project failure is mostly due to the failures in managing any of these elements (Al-Nady et al., 2013). Effective communication serves as a bridge between team members, supervisors, and project objectives, therefore considered very critical in construction management. When supervisors are distracted by their smartphones, communication interruptions happen, delaying information flow and collaboration (Zulch, 2014).

This study uses the theoretical lens of Conservation of Resources (COR) theory to build its conceptual framework. COR theory assumes that individuals strive to obtain, retain, and protect valuable resources, including physical, psychological, and emotional assets. Loss or threat of loss to any of these resources can lead to psychological distress (Hobfoll et al., 2017). Resilience, as a personal resource, plays a vital role in mitigating such distress and helping individuals adapt to stressful situations (Nielsen et al., 2012).

In recent years, researchers have increasingly explored the effects of supervisor's phubbing in organizational contexts. Previous investigations have found the negative effect of phubbing on employees' supervisor identification and contribute to psychological distress (Khan et al., 2023), reduces employee engagement (Lievaart, 2020; Roberts & David, 2017), and is linked to psychological withdrawal behaviors (Yao & Nie, 2023). However, much of the existing literature has focused on general workplace or social contexts, leaving a significant gap in understanding how supervisor's phubbing affects project-based environments, particularly in construction. To address this gap, the current study investigates the impact of supervisors' phubbing on project success within NESPAK construction projects, with a particular focus on the mediating roles of psychological distress and emotional engagement. It also examines whether employee resilience moderates the negative effects of phubbing on project outcomes. By doing so, the study aims to provide meaningful insights into improving leadership practices and communication strategies in project management.

Literature Review

Theoretical Framework- COR Theory

Supervisor's phubbing behavior at the workplace affects employee's psychological wellbeing and cause stress among workers which negatively impacts project success. This phenomenon can be best explained by Conservation of Resources (COR) theory. COR theory was the first presented by Hobfoll (1989) to give better explanation of employee's behavior in context of challenging and stressful environment. COR theory was established to describe the individual's nature to strive, obtain, retain, foster and protect things they valued (Hobfoll et al., 2017). It is a motivational theory, explaining the human behavior to acquire and conserve key resources for survival. Those key resources are individual's self-esteem, health and psychological wellbeing. Scarcity in any of these resources make someone psychologically distress (Hobfoll et al., 2017). COR has served as a framework since 1988 for understanding the significance of resilience in coping with high levels

of stress and setbacks. It is particularly effective in explaining stress and resilience within workplace settings. COR theory acknowledged the human nature of resource possession and resource gain needed for survival. Also identified the negative and positive impacts of stress and resilience (Chen et al., 2015).

The current study employs Conservation of Resources (COR) theory to construct its theoretical framework, following previous researchers who have used the same theory to examine the phubbing phenomenon. Such as Yousaf et al., (2022) applied COR theory to understand the negative impacts of phubbing at the workplace. To identify the effects of supervisor's phubbing behavior on subordinate's supervisor identification, COR theory was used by Khan et al., (2023). To know the role of employee resilience between psychological distress and project success Mubarak et al., (2022) used COR theory to construct hypotheses. As per theory, when employees face supervisor phubbing behavior at workplace, it depletes their personal resources which promotes psychological distress. Employees with psychological distress have low emotional engagement with work and low work engagement hinders the employee performance (Hobfoll et al., 2017). Consequently, supervisor phubbing behavior negatively impacts the project success. Employee resilience can be enhanced at the resources rich workplace settings, and it is the best technique to use in stressful environment. It develops self-belief, self-commitment, self-esteem among employees during anxiety, stress and depression (Bardoel & Drago, 2021).

Hypotheses Development

Supervisor's Phubbing and Project Success

In existing literature there is a notable gap in understanding the influence of supervisor phubbing on project success particularly in construction projects. Findings of Malik et al., (2021) demonstrated that communication plays a significant role in success of the construction projects. Phubbing has been studied mostly in social settings such as among friends, family, students and partners (Khan et al., 2022). In organizational context, most of work has been done analyzing the impact of supervisor phubbing on dimensions of employee performance. Previous researches have shown that there is a significant negative impact of supervisor phubbing on employees' supervisor identification via psychological distress (Khan et al., 2023). Supervisor's phubbing has also been shown as negatively associated with employee's outcomes (Yasin et al., 2023). However, the current study is focused in understanding the impact of supervisor's phubbing on project success through the involvement of employee psychological distress. This behavior reduces the supervisor employee eye-contact during conversation. Facing supervisor's phubbing behavior by employees make them think that supervisor is not giving proper attention to them. It may leads to low trust of employees on supervisor, low job engagement that results low job performance (Xu et al., 2022). The trend of having small screens in hands is increasing day by day. Although, the use of smartphones during working hours also has positive impact such as it provides bulk of information and timely communication, conversely it has a dark side too. Excessive usage of smartphones can lead to supervisor phubbing, which in turn may contribute to cyberloafing, a behavior that has been found to negatively impact job performance. Constant use of smartphone during job destroys the supervisor employee communication and subsequently their relationship (van Bommel, 2020). Proper communication is essential for timely delivery of project. Without effective communication it would be difficult to fulfil the criteria for project success. Miscommunication leads to conflicts

within teams and with stakeholders. During project, teams dependent on each other for different resources, information and knowledge (Malik et al., 2021). According to Yuda & Suyono, (2024) supervisor snubbing during working hours has negative impact on workplace dynamics and employee well-being. Phubbing done by supervisors strongly affects both employee and organization. Supervisor phubbing is negatively associated with performance of employees, which subsequently leads to lower project success. Therefore, it is assumed:

H1: Supervisor phubbing has a negative impact on project success.

Mediating role of Psychological Distress

Psychological distress is negative state of one's mental health, defined as undesirable state of emotions which results from stressful events (Khan et al., 2023). COR theory describes the influence of supervisor phubbing on employee behavior. According to the theory people depend on various resources to hold up stress, depression and anxiety. Such resources include psychological resources including self-esteem, intrinsic motivation etc. According to COR theory supervisor phubbing as a negative interpersonal interaction is major source of stress for employees. It can cause resource depletion and has significant impact on employees' psychological wellbeing. Psychological wellbeing is very important personal resource for employees (Li et al., 2016). Supervisor-subordinate communication is essential for the understanding of organizational goals and objectives. There is significant influence of supervisor-subordinate communication on employee morale (Steele & Plenty, 2015). Qin & Men, (2023) identified that supportive peer communication has significant positive association with employee's psychological wellbeing. Internal communication also plays a substantial role on employees' mental well-being. Therefore, it is assumed that supervisor phubbing behavior depletes the intensity of communication between supervisor and subordinate and positively influenced employee psychological distress.

H2: Supervisor phubbing positively associated with psychological distress.

Construction projects are based on stressful environment, where every worker work hard for the safe delivery of project within set budget (Bowen et al., 2017). Employee strong mental wellbeing is very important aspect at work environment. Employee positive mental and physical health is critical factors for organizational success and performance. Positive psychological wellbeing promotes positive outcomes at work settings (Kundi et al., 2021). The influence of employee psychological distress on project success needs more attention. Previous studies on psychological wellbeing have demonstrated that psychological distress has negative impact on employee performance (Daniel, 2019).

Chiocchio et al., (2010) found the positive relationship between time pressure and psychological stress. Project is itself very stressful activity. In projects, there are different challenges that contribute to psychological distress affecting project success. Supervisor phubbing depletes the employee's psychological resources affecting employee's mental health. Consequently, employees get short of those psychological resources that are needed to perform well (Mubarak et al., 2022). It is explored by Mubarak et al., (2022) that psychological distress has significant negative impact on project success, resilience playing a critical role in this relationship. Project performance is key factor for analysis of project success. Anxiety, depression and such negative emotions negatively influenced the project performance (Wu et al., 2018). During Covid-19, a research undertaken by

Olatoye et al., (2023) showed that psychological wellbeing of workers is crucial for strong projects outcomes. From the above arguments and evidences, the study hypothesized:

H3: Psychological distress negatively associated with project success.

Addiction of mobile phone is greater cause of psychological distress (Lian et al., 2021). At the workplace, disrespectful, ignorant behavior of supervisor is one of the major factors for employee psychological distress. Supervisor phubbing behavior reduces the psychological needs of employees that cause stress, anxiety and depression which results low productivity (Khan et al., 2023). Furthermore Yao & Nie, (2023) identified that supervisor phubbing not only increases stress among employees but also becomes the reason for employee psychological withdrawal behavior. From the above evidence, it is identified that supervisor phubbing is associated with employee psychological distress. At the workplace, despite of many mental health issues, depression, burnout and psychological distress are also common (Schultz et al., 2015). So based on the previous literature, it is assumed that psychological distress mediates the relationship between supervisor phubbing and project success.

H4: Psychological distress mediates the relationship between supervisor phubbing and project success.

Mediating role of Emotional Engagement

Employee engagement refers to the employee behavior that shows one's physically, emotionally and cognitively committed to work (Bedarkar & Pandita, 2014). Employee engagement comprises of three factors such as cognitive engagement, emotional engagement and behavioral engagement. Cognitive engagement refers to "the energy of one's towards achieving organizational outcomes". Emotional engagement is defined as "employee's intensity to invest mental energy for the achievement of organizational outcomes". And the behavioral engagement, is defined as "having positive psychological state to behave in a manner to perform well to achieve organizational outcomes" (Kosaka & Sato, 2020). Employees are more emotionally engaged when they have supervisor's support. When supervisor has proper interaction and communication with subordinates it will increase their emotional engagement. Studies have also found that internal communication is essential for emotional engagement (Imam et al., 2023). Although most of investigations have been carried on work engagement, however little attention has been given to emotional engagement Emotional engagement can be measured by how positive employees feel about their job (LaGree et al., 2023). For organizational success it is important to create an emotional culture in an organization. Emotional culture refers to a workplace environment where individuals feel important, appreciated, and take pride in their work. The prior explorations have shown that responsive leadership communication is positively associated with emotional culture (Men & Yue, 2019). Therefore, it is concluded that getting full attention from supervisors is important for better communication which leads to enhance emotional engagement. Consequently, this is hypothesized that there exists negative relationship between supervisor phubbing and emotional engagement.

H5: Supervisor phubbing negatively impacts the emotional engagement.

Supervisor's phubbing causes psychological distress which in return affects emotional engagement. People feel motivated and engaged in favorable environment where they are allowed to openly express themselves. Successful projects are expected to be completed on time, at minimal operational cost, and of the highest quality. To achieve this, employees require a supportive and positive work environment. Employees who have strong connections with their supervisor are more engaged with work contributing to project success (Nawaz & Qayyum, 2022). Individual performance is crucial for the project's success or failure. It is found that employee engagement greatly influences the success of the organization. Emotionally engaged employees produce more positive outcomes in the workplace. Such employees help to finish project within set cost, schedule and deliver good quality of the project (Lai et al., 2020). From the evidence discussed the following hypothesis is generated:

H6: Emotional engagement significantly and positively impacts the project success.

When employees face distractions from their supervisor, they feel demotivated and their engagement level drops leading to lower their performance (Siddiqui & Sahar, 2019). Earlier investigations have shown that employee engagement is crucial in enhancing the performance of employees. There exists a positive relationship between employee engagement and employee performance. In simple words, When employees are emotionally engaged with their tasks, roles, or work, they are more likely to produce positive outcomes (Schullery, 2013). Therefore, effective communication between supervisors and subordinates helps clearly define roles and goals, fostering stronger emotional connection among employees to their tasks. This emotional engagement, in turn, enhances employee performance and increases the likelihood of project success. Hence, it is hypothesized that emotional engagement mediates the relationship between supervisor phubbing and project success.

H7: Emotional engagement mediates the relationship between supervisor phubbing and project success.

Moderating role of Employee Resilience

At workplace, employee need resilience (the capacity to rebound setbacks, failures and depression) to perform well in challenging environment Projects are highly dependent on personal characteristics of manager (Al-Abrow et al., 2019). Researchers have identified that employees' mental well-being can be enhanced by different tools and techniques such as resilience, mindfulness and regular workout (Bardoel & Drago, 2021). A strong mental health improves employee performance. From previous literature it is proved that employees with resilience have capacity to move on and recover from psychological distress; low level of employee's psychological stress leads to more chances of project success. As projects involves hurdles and challenges due to different factors, one of them is psychological distress, employees with high level of resilience better cope with those challenges (Mubarak et al., 2022).

Construction industry face most disruptions and challenges because of its uncertain nature. Resilience has been studied in many other fields but the importance of resilience in construction projects in still under studied (Angeler & Allen, 2016). Construction projects face many adversities such as budget and time fluctuations. Resilience may lead to promising outcomes under such uncertain circumstances. Earlier literature has also demonstrated that resilience has positive impact

on project success (Malik et al., 2021; Sascha Fey, 2022). Therefore, it is assumed that by introducing employee resilience between in relationship psychological distress of employees would be minimized.

H8: Employee resilience moderates the relationship between psychological distress and project success.

Figure 1
 Conceptual Framework
 Adapted from Khan et al., (2023) and Mubarak et al., (2022)

Materials and Methods

Population and Sampling

This study is focused on the construction division of the National Engineering Services Pakistan (NESPAK) to investigate the impact of supervisor’s phubbing on the success of construction projects. Given the complex nature of construction projects, effective communication is essential for achieving key project outcomes such as cost efficiency, timely delivery, and quality performance (Malik et al., 2021). To select participants, purposive sampling was employed, a method where samples are chosen based on predefined criteria (Andrade, 2021). A similar sampling approach was used by Koc and Caliskan (2023) in their research on phubbing in educational settings.

For this study, the following inclusion criteria were applied to identify the target population:

Employment status: Participants must be currently employed full-time (Roberts & David, 2017).

Smartphone usage policy: Supervisors must be permitted to use smartphones during work hours (Yasin, 2021).

Professional contribution: Participants must have effectively contributed to multiple successfully completed projects (Gunduz & Yahya, 2015).

Based on these criteria, 132 employees were identified as meeting the eligibility requirements, and data were subsequently collected from them.

Variables & Measures

All variables are measured by using already determined five-point Likert scales to ensure reliability and accuracy.

Supervisor Phubbing: To measure this variable 9- items Likert scale was used which is adopted from Roberts & David, (2017).

Psychological Distress: To measure this variable 6-items Likert scale is used which is adopted from Kessler et al., (2002).

Emotional Engagement: To measure this variable 4-items Likert scale is used, which is adopted from Kosaka & Sato, (2020).

Employee Resiliene: To measure this variable 14-items Likert scale is used, which is adopted from Näswall et al., (2013).

Project Success: To measure this variable 14-items Likert scale is used, which is adopted from Hughes et al., (2004).

Findings

Respondents' Profile

The demographic profile of the respondents shows that male respondents were comparatively larger in number than female. It is also found that a high percentage of respondents lies between age of 31 to 40. Furthermore, most of respondents have work experience in the range of 14 to 25 years.

Table 1
Demographic Profile

Measure	Item	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	101	76
	Female	31	24
Age (years)	Under 25	3	2
	26 - 35	74	56
	36 - 45	55	42
Work Experience (years)	4 - 6	38	29
	7 - 8	80	61
	10 - 12	14	10

Descriptive Statistics

The descriptive statistics show that respondents have a moderate level of agreement on supervisor phubbing and its effects (ranging from 2.6 to 3.5). All the measures of standard deviation are close to 1.5, also indicating that responses vary moderately.

Table 2

Descriptive Statistics

Variable Name	Mean	Std. Deviation
Supervisor Phubbing	2.6	1.0
Project Success	3.2	1.2
Psychological Distress	2.6	1.0
Emotional Engagement	3.1	1.3
Employee Resilience	3.5	1.0

Correlation Analysis

The correlation between supervisor phubbing and project success is -0.864, indicating a strong negative relationship. Likewise, the correlation between supervisor phubbing and psychological distress is 0.767, reflecting a strong positive association. A strong negative correlation of -0.805 is also observed between supervisor phubbing and emotional engagement. Additionally, supervisor phubbing shows a strong negative correlation of -0.73 with employee resilience. These findings suggest that there are strong relationships among all the variables examined in the study.

Table 3

Correlation

Correlation	Supervisor Phubbing	Psychological Distress	Emotional Engagement	Project Success
Supervisor Phubbing	1			
Psychological Distress	0.767**	1		
Emotional Engagement	-0.805**	-0.688**	1	
Project Success	-0.864**	-0.813**	0.814**	1

Note: ** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Measurement Model

The study uses a factor analysis to identify the latent components that influence project success. All variables Supervisor Phubbing, Psychological Distress, Emotional Engagement, Employee

Resilience and Project Success showed higher factor loadings.

Table 4

Confirmatory Factor Analysis

Variables	Indicators	Factor loadings	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	AVE
Supervisor Phubbing	SP1	.858	0.867	0.853	0.764
	SP2	.912			
	SP3	.828			
	SP4	.931			
	SP5	.952			
	SP6	.915			
	SP7	.653			
	SP8	.910			
	SP9	.871			
Psychological Distress	PD1	.883	0.934	0.955	0.860
	PD2	.894			
	PD3	.850			
	PD4	.899			
	PD5	.883			
	PD6	.890			
Emotional Engagement	EE1	.839	0.910	0.978	0.919
	EE2	.907			
	EE3	.880			
	EE4	.904			
Employee Resilience	ER1	.914	0.950	0.990	0.880
	ER2	.948			
	ER3	.898			
	ER4	.937			
	ER5	.934			
	ER6	.953			
	ER7	.944			
	ER8	.934			
	ER9	.958			
	ER10	.947			
	ER11	.921			
	ER12	.946			
	ER13	.936			
	ER14	.962			
Project Success	C1	.944	0.881	0.889	0.766

C2	.924
C3	.918
C4	.936
C5	.933
QTY1	.942
QTY2	.944
QTY3	.936
QTY4	.922
SCH1	.923
SCH2	.941
SCH3	.919
SCH4	.943
SCH5	.904

Note(s): SP = Supervisor Phubbing, PD = Psychological Distress, EE = Emotional Engagement, ER = Employee Resilience, PS= Project Success

Construct Validity

Construct validity is tested through three indicators such as Cronbach's alpha, Composite reliability and average variance extracted (AVE).

Cronbach's Alpha: According to Tavakol and Dennick (2011), Cronbach's alpha value between 0.70 and 0.80 indicates good reliability, values between 0.80 and 0.90 reflect very good reliability, and values above 0.90 signify excellent reliability. In the present study, all Cronbach's alpha values exceed 0.80, indicating that the measures used demonstrate very good to excellent reliability.

Composite Reliability: The acceptable value of composite reliability is 0.7 (Hair et al., 2021). In this study, all the values are above 0.85, indicating a strong composite reliability.

Average Variance Extracted (AVE): Average Variance Extract is used to measure the convergent validity. The value of AVE is ranges between 0 – 1, value more towards 1 indicates greater reliability, AVE value must be greater than or equals to 0.5 (Hair et al., 2021). In this study all the values are above 0.75, indicating a strong validity.

Discriminant Validity

Heterotrait Monotrait ratio (HTMT) is the statistical technique used to measure the discriminant validity among the latent variables. It is used to measure the correlation among the two latent variables. The value of HTMT must be less than 0.85. Values greater than 0.85 shows lack of discriminant validity among the latent variables (Henseler et al., 2015). The HTMT values of the current study are less than 0.85 which indicates the more correlation among two latent variables.

Table 5

Discriminant Validity

	EE	ER	PD	PS	SP
EE					
ER	0.758				
PD	0.718	0.617			
PS	0.833	0.787	0.841		
SP	0.851	0.740	0.815	0.886	

Note(s): SP = Supervisor Phubbing, PD = Psychological Distress, EE = Emotional Engagement, ER = Employee Resilience, PS= Project Success

Hypotheses Testing

The results of the analysis provide meaningful insights regarding how supervisor phubbing affects project success directly and indirectly. H1 directly tests impact of supervisor phubbing on project success. The direct effect of supervisor phubbing on project success is negatively significant (path coefficient = 0.289) implying that supervisor's engagement with the phone during working hours has negative impact on project success. Similarly, the study explored the impact of supervisor phubbing in psychological distress, it is found that supervisor phubbing significantly influences psychological distress (path coefficient = 0.777). H3 investigated the influence of psychological distress on project success, it is noted that there is a significant negative effect on project success (path coefficient = 0.303). H5 assesses the direct effect of supervisor phubbing on emotional engagement, with a path coefficient of 0.821. This indicates that higher levels of supervisor phubbing are associated with lower levels of emotional engagement. Furthermore, H6 confirms that notable emotional engagement of employees leads to greater project success with 0.161 path coefficient.

Table 6

Hypotheses testing Results

Hypotheses	Hypothesized Relationship	Total Direct Effects	Result
H1	SP → PS	-0.289**	H1 is supported
H2	SP → PD	0.777***	H2 is supported
H3	PD → PS	-0.303***	H3 is supported
H5	SP → EE	-0.821***	H5 is supported
H6	EE → PS	0.161*	H6 is supported

Note(s): SP = Supervisor Phubbing, PD = Psychological Distress, EE = Emotional Engagement, PS= Project Success

Mediation Testing

The findings revealed that introducing psychological distress as a mediator between supervisor phubbing and project success alters the strength of the relationship. This indicates that psychological distress partially mediates the link between supervisor phubbing and project success ($\beta = -0.236, p < .0001$), accepting H4. Similarly, the emotional engagement partially mediates the relationship between supervisor phubbing and project success ($\beta = -0.132, p < .01$). Hence, H7 is also accepted implying emotional engagement mediates the relationship between supervisor phubbing and project success.

Table 7

Mediation Testing Results

	a	b	c	a * b	Results	Comments
SP → PD → PS	0.777***	0.303***	-0.289**	-0.236***	Supporting H4	Partially mediating
SP → EE → PS	-0.821***	0.161*	-0.289**	-0.132*	Supporting H7	Partially mediating

Note: SP = Supervisor Phubbing, PD = Psychological Distress, EE = Emotional Engagement,

Moderation Testing

This test investigated whether employee resilience is important for the relationship of psychological distress and project success. Results show that employee resilience significantly changes the direction of relationship between psychological distress and project success. Employee resilience moderates this path significantly.

Table 8

Regression Results for the Dependent Variable (PD)

Outcome Variable: PD

Predictor	Coefficient (B)	Standard error (SE)	t	p
Constant	-2.0542	0.1621	-12.67	.000
SP	0.8001	0.0587	13.64	.000

Note: SP= Supervisor Phubbing, PD = Psychological Distress

Model Summary: $R = .7672, R^2 = .5885, F(1, 130) = 185.95, p < .001$

The impact of the independent variable (SP) on the mediator (PD) is estimated via this regression. The findings indicate that increases in SP are linked to increased PD, with a substantial positive influence of SP on PD ($B = 0.8001, p < .001$). 58.85% of the variance in PD can be explained by the model.

Table 9

Regression Results for the Dependent Variable (PS)

Outcome Variable: PS

Predictor	Coefficient (B)	Standard Error (SE)	t	p
Constant	4.2650	0.2107	20.24	.000
SP	-0.4257	0.0764	-5.57	.000
PD	-0.3671	0.0612	-6.00	.000
ER	0.3835	0.0701	5.47	.000
PD × ER (Int_1)	-0.0773	0.0528	-1.46	.146

Note: SP = Supervisor Phubbing, PD = Psychological Distress, ER = Employee Resilience, PS = Project Success

Model Summary R = .9178, R² = .8423, F(4, 127) = 169.64, p < .001

The effects of SP, PD, ER, and the interaction PD×ER on PS are estimated via this regression. While ER has a strong favorable impact on PS, SP and PD both have considerable negative impacts. The PD × ER interaction term, however, is not significant (p = .146), suggesting that ER does not significantly moderate the PD → PS link.

Table 10

Conditional Indirect Effects of SP on PS via PD at Levels of ER

ER Level (W)	Indirect Effect	Boot SE	95% CI (BootLLCI – BootULCI)	Significant?
-1.0399 (Low)	-0.2294	0.0873	[-0.4154, -0.0688]	Yes
0.0000 (Mean)	-0.2938	0.0733	[-0.4465, -0.1558]	Yes
1.0399 (High)	-0.3581	0.0925	[-0.5530, -0.1921]	Yes

Note: SP = Supervisor Phubbing, PD = Psychological Distress, ER = Employee Resilience

According to these findings, SP indirectly affects PS through PD at three moderator ER levels. Given that all three effects are statistically significant, it is possible that mediation occurs at all ER levels.

Table 11

Index of Moderated Mediation

Index of Moderated Mediation	Boot SE	95% CI (BootLLCI – BootULCI)	Significant?
-0.0618	0.0501	[-0.1613, 0.0355]	No

This index determines if ER significantly alters the indirect effect of SP on PS through PD. However, moderation mediation is not statistically significant because the confidence interval contains zero.

Discussion

This study investigated the impact of supervisor's phubbing on project success in construction industry through the lens of Conservation of Resources (COR) theory (Hobfoll, 1989), whereas also examining the mediating roles of psychological distress and emotional engagement, and the moderating role of employee resilience. All hypotheses were grounded in the Conservation of Resources (COR) framework, and the results of the current investigation provide empirical support for each of them. The findings underpin and extend COR theory by establishing how seemingly negligible workplace behaviors such as a supervisor's engagement with a mobile device can lead towards a constant flow of resource loss, ultimately preceding harmful consequences at both individual and project levels.

COR theory hypothesizes that individuals try to acquire, retain, and protect their psychological and emotional resources. However, whenever there is a threat of depletion to these resources, they go through stress, which negatively affects their performance and health. The present investigation adds a novel dimension to this theory by placing supervisor's phubbing as a delicate however noteworthy workplace stressor. When supervisors develop the practice of using their mobile phones during face-to-face communications, their behavior is perceived as disrespectful by employees, leading to a depletion of psychological resources such as trust, perceived support, and self-worth. Ultimately such resource loss is demonstrated in two important ways, as also shown by earlier studies. Considering the previous work of Roberts & David (2017), supervisor's phubbing leads to high psychological distress, which subsequently decreases employee potential to concentrate, cooperate, and get engaged with project tasks, particularly in complex and high-pressure environments like construction.

Moreover, emotional engagement, a vital element of employee involvement, was found to partially mediate the relationship between phubbing and project outcomes. This also provides support to research which suggests that emotional connection to work, along with supervisor's attitude, plays a significant role in improving employee performance (Reina et al., 2018). When employees get the feeling of being disregarded or mistreated due to phubbing, their emotional bond with their work deteriorates, subsequently leading towards low motivation and productivity. Furthermore, the results have demonstrated that employee resilience moderates the negative effects of psychological distress on project success. Resilient employees have the capability to recover from the stress caused by supervisor phubbing more quickly and have the potential to maintain their performance levels. This supports the notion of COR theory, which states that collection of resources assists individuals to deal with the difficulties. Considering the current scenario, resilience operates as a personal resource that cushions the impact of stress and maintains focused behavior in challenging situations (Ríos-Risquez et al., 2018).

The findings of the current investigation have important implications for workplace practices and project management. Firstly, the most important point for supervisors is to make them aware of the fact that their excessive mobile usage during working hours is negatively perceived by their employees. Although mobile phones are essential tools in modern project environments, however

misuse of such devices particularly during interactions with subordinates indicates distraction and distorts the effectiveness of communication. Organizations should try to introduce formal protocols of communication at workplace, especially incorporating designated phone-free meeting spaces, training sessions regarding mobile phone usage etc. Furthermore, Businesses should build a “smart phone safe” area where supervisors and employees can use their personal phone for quick interactions in their free time. Therefore, supervisors clear about when and where mobile phones are restricted (Roberts & David, 2017). In addition to that, the study emphasizes the significance of developing employee resilience through training programs, peer support mechanisms, and stress management workshops, as findings of the study suggested that resilient employees would be less sensitive towards the negative behavior of supervisors at the workplace than the employees with lower level of resilience. These methods would help to reduce mental stress and enhance the psychological wellbeing of employees. Such techniques will improve the performance of employees (Mubarak et al., 2022). Organizations can protect themselves from the harmful consequences of supervisor inattentiveness by increasing employee capacity to cope up with resource-draining behaviors. As, emotional disengagement can silently disrupt project efforts, even though having high technical competencies, therefore, emotional engagement can be fostered through recognition, reliable supervisor support and trust building.

This research explores a seemingly insignificant yet deeper organizational challenge, i.e. deterioration of workplace environment and loss of employee attention through apparently trivial behavior like phubbing. Industries like construction which require fast paced working dynamics and high technological advancements, disconnection from employees may create a big loss. Although digital tools have become the necessity today, their misuse, especially by those who sit at leadership positions, can unintentionally lead to disengagement, disrespect, and a breakdown in team cohesion. The current study emphasizes the idea that the issue of phubbing at workplace needs to be addressed not only by regulating the phone usage but also developing conscious leadership and strengthening a culture of presence, respect, and psychological safety. This also suggests that on the longer run change requires not only in the policies of any organization but also investment in leadership that stresses emotional intelligence and attentiveness. Organizations may build stronger teams and successful project outcomes by creating a workplace where interpersonal respect is giving precedence alongside performance. An employee who feels respected and valued is more likely to remain loyal to the organization and contribute consistently to successful outcomes.

Contributions

This study contributes to organizational behavior literature in several ways. Firstly, it brings the concept of phubbing as an organizational level issue, which was not recognized as such before. Although earlier researchers considered phubbing at interpersonal or consumer level, this exploration establishes its significance in structured and task-oriented project environments. Secondly, this research particularly joins two formerly disconnected domains: stress theory and project management, by incorporating COR theory with project success frameworks. It has demonstrated that soft behavioral factors are generally ignored in high technical fields like construction industry, however such seemingly insignificant behaviors such as phubbing may greatly influence hard outcomes such as cost, schedule, and quality. Also, the moderated mediation

model extends existing theory by showing that resilience is not only a personal trait but a key strategic resource. In resource-depleting environments, such as those characterized by poor communication or digital distraction, resilience enables employees to maintain alignment with project goals.

Limitations & Future Implications

The current investigation has used cross-sectional data due to considerations of time, cost, and accessibility. However, this methodological choice may limit the generalizability of the findings. Also, this research particularly focused on the construction sector to explore the influence of supervisor's phubbing on project success. The impact of supervisor's phubbing could also be investigated in other sectors, such as information technology, healthcare, and research and development. Future research is encouraged to incorporate additional variables, such as trust and employee resilience, to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon. Moreover, this study did not distinguish between work-related and personal mobile phone use, an aspect that future studies could explore to yield more nuanced insights. Employee-related variables such as psychological distress, emotional engagement, and resilience were measured using self-reported data. Given the reliance on self-reported data, the findings may be subject to social desirability bias. To mitigate this, future studies might consider using multisource data. Additionally, employing longitudinal designs is recommended to enhance the generalizability and robustness of the results.

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